

Calculating the Smarandache Numbers

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Abstract

The Smarandache Numbers are:

1,2,3,4,5,3,7,4,6,5,11,4,13,7,5,6,17,6,19,5,7,11,23,4,10,13,9,7,29,5,31,8,11,17,7,6,37,
19,13,5,41,7,43,11,6,23,47,6,14,10,17,13,53,9,11,7,19,29,59,5,61,31,7,8,13,11,67,17,
23,7,71, 6,73,37,10,19,11,13,79,6,9,41,83,7, ...

and defined as the smallest integer m such that n divides $m!$ Finding the exact value of $a(n)$ is an open problem, and this paper presents an effective algorithm for determining the value of $a(n)$.

Keywords

Smarandache functions, factorial, prime numbers

Introduction

The process involved is fairly simple, and we need to know the factorisation of n . From this factorisation, it is possible to exactly calculate by which m each prime is satisfied, i.e. the correct number of exponents appears for the first time. The largest of these values gives $a(n)$.

Satisfying p^k

To satisfy p^k , we find the lowest m such that p^k divides $m!$.

For example, if we look at $3^4=81$, then $m=9$ suffices and is also the lowest possible value of m we can achieve.

We can see that $m=9$ suffices, as $9!=1.2.3.4.5.6.7.8.9$, of which 3,6 and 9 are multiples of 3, and 9 happens to be 3^2 . As 3, 6 and 9 are the first multiples of 3, this implies $m=9$ is minimal.

The key to finding m lies in the value of k , and with the distribution of 3's over the integers.

The pattern of divisibility by 3, beginning with 1, is;

0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 2 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 2 0 0 1 0 0 1 0 0 3 0

For the purpose of the Smarandache numbers, we can remove the 0's from this, as we are only concerned with accumulating enough 3's.

(A) 1 1 2 1 1 2 1 1 3 1 1 2 1 1 2 1 1 3 1 1 2 1 1 2 1 1 4 1

The pattern present here can be generalized at a basic level to allow us to calculate the values of the sums whenever a number appears for the first time.

This gives us the sub-sequences 1, 112, 112112113, etc..., and we are interested in the sums of these, i.e.:

(B) 1, 4, 13, 40 ...

This is the partial sums of $1+3+9+27+\dots$, and this is result of evaluating $(3^n-1)/2$.

Now we can deduce the value of m from k , where does k appear in B ? Our k in the example was 4, and this appears as $B(2)$. This means that to reach 3^4 we need 3 terms from A ($=3^{(2-1)}$), and multiplying by 3 gives the answer we require of 9.

But how about 3^{333} ? To calculate m for this, we reduce in by as many possible of the terms of A .

A fuller list of A is:

```
(pari/gp code)
three(n)=(3^n-1)/2
for (n=1,8,print1(three(n),""))
```

1,4,13,40,121,364,1093,3280,

364 is too large, but 121 is Ok. $333-121=212$, and again $212-121=91$.

121 is $A(5)$, so the data collected so far is $[2*5]$

Continuing, $91-2*40=11$, and $11-2*4=3$, and $3=1*3$, thus we have the data $[2*5, 2*4, 2*2, 3*1]$.

To interpret this data, we just re-apply it to the distribution of 3's. $2*5$ means that we need $2*3^4$ consecutive multiples of 3 – by this stage we have satisfied 3^{242} . $2*4$ means that we add a further $2*3^3$ multiples of 3, $2*2$ means that we add a further $2*3^1$ multiples of 3, and finally we add $3*1$ multiples of 3.

The whole sum is therefore $2*81+2*27+2*3+3*1=162+54+6+3=225$, and this gives us the answer directly: $(225*3)! = 675!$ is the smallest factorial that 3^{333} divides.

This can be proven with a small Pari program:

```
? for(i=1,2000,if(i!%3^333==0,print1(i);break))
675
```

Calculating $a(n)$

Then we need to calculate the m value for each prime and exponent, and a(n) is the largest.

This Pari/GP code performs the necessary calculations

```
{
findm(x,y)=local(m,n,x1);
m=0;n=1;x1=x-1;
while (((x^n-1)/x1)<=y,n++);n--;
while (y>0,
while (((x^n-1)/x1)<=y,y-=((x^n-1)/x1);m+=(x^(n-1)));n--);
x*m
}
```

This is the findm() function. n is boosted until larger than necessary, and then trimmed down one so that it must be less than or equal to y. Then y is decreased by the largest possible value of $(x^n-1)/(x-1)$ possible until $y=0$. m is continually incremented throughout this process as appropriate, and the returned value is $x*m$.

```
{
smarandache(n)=local(f,fl,ms);
if (n==1,1,
f=factor(n);fl=length(f[,1]);
ms=vector(fl,i,0);
for (i=1,fl,ms[i]=findm(f[i,1],f[i,2]));
vecmax(ms))
}
```

The smarandache() function returns 1 if n is 1, otherwise it creates the ms vector of lowest possible m values, and returns the largest value.

The program results in this data:

```
?for (i=1,100,print1(smarandache(i)," "))
1,2,3,4,5,3,7,4,6,5,11,4,13,7,5,6,17,6,19,5,7,11,23,4,10,13,9,7,29,5,31,8,11,17,
7,6,37,19,13,5,41,7,43,11,6,23,47,6,14,10,17,13,53,9,11,7,19,29,59,5,61,31,7,8,1
3,11,67,17,23,7,71,6,73,37,10,19,11,13,79,6,9,41,83,7,17,43,29,11,89,6,13,23,31,
47,19,8,97,14,11,10,
```

which give a 100% correlation with the sequence given in the abstract.

At 100Mhz, it takes about 1 minute to generate the sequence to $n=10000$.

Reference:

Neil Sloane, The Encyclopaedia of Integer Sequences, Sequence # A002034,
[http://www.research.att.com/cgi-
bin/access.cgi/as/njas/sequences/eisA.cgi?Anum=A002034](http://www.research.att.com/cgi-bin/access.cgi/as/njas/sequences/eisA.cgi?Anum=A002034)